

**IMPROVING THE UNIFORMITY OF ACCOUNTING AND TAXATION
IN UZBEKISTAN**

Khabiba Arifkhanova

State Tax Committee

Doctoral student of the Fiscal Institute

khabiba.arifkhanova@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT: Improving the system of accounting and reporting in the public sector based on international standards of accounting, further increasing the country's rating based on the adaptation of methodological aspects of accounting to the names generally accepted in international practice; increase information coverage and transparency of reports in public finance management; ensuring the integration of financial and statistical reports; is to increase the volume of foreign investments and donor funds in the context of the globalization of international relations. This article is about improving the reconciliation of accounting and tax accounting.

Key words: Budget, budget organization, International Accounting Standards (IAS), public sector, Fiscal year, passive account, active account, financial results, contract

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, in the context of reforms in the budget and tax policy of our country, measures to reduce the funding of budget organizations from the budget show the importance of extra-budget funds of budget organizations. In this regard, the accepted regulatory and legal frameworks are a clear proof of this. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the most important priority tasks of the development of our country in 2019, "The need to further improve the system of effective use of budget funds, the quality and quantity of any program or project that is allocated from the budget it was emphasized that there should be result-oriented indicators consisting of indicators.

It is known that with the reduction of tax rates or the abolition of certain taxes, the budget amount will definitely decrease. It is possible to eliminate this through effective tax administration and ensure budget stability. It is our first task to achieve this," said President Sh. It was mentioned by Mirziyoyev. In the process of budget implementation, accounting is established in budget organizations for continuous accounting of the formation and spending of state

budget funds and extra-budgetary funds of budget organizations, their documentation and systematic formation of information.

Reasonable and effective use of budget funds, prevention of budget deficit is one of the urgent issues. "Certainly, the state budget is not without measure, it is necessary to strictly save the funds, ensure that they are used for the specified purpose and rationally. This is an obvious and undeniable truth," said President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his speeches. Budget organizations are considered the main consumer of budget funds, organize the expenses of the state budget and are financed from the budget based on the cost estimate. Also, in accordance with the law, the budget organization makes expenses within the budget estimates for extra-budget funds, indicating the sources of organization and directions of use.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Special attention is being paid to the purposeful and rational use of funds in the process of reforms in the budget system. In this regard, the study of foreign experiences of budget accounting is of particular importance in conducting scientific research. Also, improving budget accounting and reporting requires in-depth study of foreign experiences of budget accounting, advantages and stages of their application. Improvement of accounting and reporting in the public sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan was defined as one of the main directions of the reforms implemented in the budget system and the concept was adopted. According to the concept, the adoption of Budget accounting standards was determined.

The application of international accounting standards in the public sector in the countries of higher quality financial reports creates a great opportunity to evaluate the results of the public sector activities, increases the transparency of information, ensures a high level of integration of financial accounting and statistical reports into the budget, due to the increase in the reliability and completeness of the information, the state enables effective management of assets, an opportunity is created to compare financial reports with financial reports of other countries, increase the size of foreign investments and see donor funds based on understanding the country's obligations in the context of globalization of international relations and how it is managed with its own resources, as well as the financial situation allows to increase. From the above, it can be said that International Accounting Standards in the public sector are more widely used and recognized throughout the world. Even some countries are using the International Accounting Standards in the Public Sector without

changes as their own standards, and some are introducing some changes based on the characteristics of the country.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Accounting and tax are closely related fields that are essential for the proper functioning of any business or organization. Accounting is the process of recording, classifying, and summarizing financial transactions, while tax is the process of determining and paying taxes owed to the government.

Accounting is the foundation of tax preparation. In order to determine how much tax a business or organization owes; accurate and detailed financial records must be kept. This includes recording all income, expenses, and assets, as well as tracking any deductions or credits that may be available. Without accurate accounting and bookkeeping it would be impossible to accurately determine the amount of taxes owed.

Furthermore, accounting and tax go hand in hand when it comes to compliance. Tax laws and regulations are subjected to constant change, and it is the responsibility of businesses and organizations to stay informed and comply with these changes. Accountants and tax professionals work together to ensure that a business or organization is in tax compliance with laws and regulations. This includes preparing and filing tax returns, as well as responding to any audits or other tax-related inquiries.

CONCLUSION

Today, in Uzbekistan, the work and research carried out on the basis of plans aimed at the unification of accounting and taxation are justified, new tasks are defined and formed on the basis of planning, based on the similarities between accounting and taxation.

The use of international standards of accounting and taxation in the public sector in the countries creates a great opportunity to prepare higher quality financial reports as well as to evaluate the results of public sector activities, increases the transparency of information, ensures a high level of integration of financial accounting, tax and statistical reports into the budget, information reliability and due to the increase in completeness, it allows effective management of state assets, it is possible to compare financial reports with financial reports of other countries, increase the volume of foreign investments based on the understanding of the obligations of the country in the context of the globalization of international relations and how it is managed with its own resources, as well as the financial situation and increase donor funds and increase the level of financial discipline in the public sector.

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